

Mechanism of Ziegler-Natta Polymerization—Role of Organometallic Compound during Polymerization*

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The structure of polymerization centres for catalyst system $TiCl_3/AlR_3$, AlR_2X , $AlRX_2$ ($R=Et, n-Bu, Dec, X=Cl, Br, I$) has been proposed to be bimetallic for propene polymerization. The essential role of organometallic compound

where Y can be R or X as the component of polymerisation centres of working Ziegler-Natta catalysts has been suggested on the basis of experimental results obtained from new kinetic technique of elimination and substitution of organometallic compound during polymerization

THE structure of polymerization centers on the surface of titanium trichloride formed with organometallic compound has not been yet settled whether it is a bimetallic one or a monometallic one. The structure (I) proposed by Furukawa et al.¹ and Natta et al.² is based on that polymerization activity and stereospecificity of catalyst system are affected by the kind of the organometallic compound. On the other hand the monometallic structure (II) proposed by Cossee et al.³ has been supported by the existence of stereoactive transition metal compound systems^{4,5} and especially by recent finding of Ti- and Zr-complexes⁶. The effect of organo-metallic compound, which has been held to be the evidence for the bimetallic theory, is considered by the workers who prefer the latter structure as the result from changes in the degree of alkylation or reduction of the titanium trichloride rather than differences resulting from coordination of a different organometallic compound.

Although many workers prefer the monometallic theory, the present author proposes here the following bimetallic structure (III) as the working polymerization centers during propene polymerizations with the typical catalyst systems, $TiCl_3/AlR_3$, AlR_2X , $AlRX_2$ ($R=Et, n-Bu, Dec, X=Cl, Br, I$).

Kinetic characters of Catalyst System in Propene Polymerization :

A reported and summarized in the author's monograph⁷, kinetic curve (polymerization rate-time curve) of propene polymerization with $TiCl_3$ and organometallic compound A shows its characteristic character in accordance with the structure of A. For example, in the cases with $A=AlR_3$, the kinetic curves are one with a rate maximum R_m followed by a gradual decrease to the stationary rate R_∞ while in the cases with $A=AlEt_2Cl$ and $AlEt_2Br$, they are monotonic increasing curves to the stationary rate. The increasing rate to R_m or R_∞ , gradual decreasing rate to R_∞ from R_m , values of R_m and R_∞ , values of the respective rate constants of changing rates are different characters of different kinds of organometallic compound A, as can be seen from Table 1. The kinetics of initial increase of polymerization rate depends on the order of addition of monomer M and A; case A ($TiCl_3+A+M$) and case B ($TiCl_3+M+A$). The kinetics of the initial increasing rate are

$$(dR/dt)_0 = k_1 P^2 (K[A]/1 + K[A]) \quad \text{case A (1)}$$

$$\text{and } (dR/dt)_0 = k_2 P [A], \quad \text{case B (2)}$$

In the cases with $AlEt_2X$ the long induction period masks the initial kinetics in the case A. The gradual decrease to R_∞ from R_m is independent of the order of addition and represented by

$$R - R_\infty = (R_0 - R_\infty) \exp(-k_3 t) \quad (3)$$

where k_3 is independent of the concentration of alkylaluminum $[A]$ and almost of propene pressure P. The kinetics of the stationary polymerization rate is expressed by

$$R_\infty = k_p P (K[A]/1 + K[A]) \quad (4)$$

Although those kinetic data themselves are important ones for the mechanistic discussion, the

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TABLE 1—KINETIC DATA OF VARIOUS CATALYSTS (TiCl₃ + AlR₃Y) AT 41°C

AlR ₃ Y	Case A		Case B		R _∞	k _p (g-C ₃ H ₆ / g-TiCl ₃ .h.atm)	E _p (k cal/ mole)	k ₁ (g-C ₃ H ₆ / g-TiCl ₃ .h ² .atm ²)	E ₁											
	R _m (g-C ₃ H ₆ / g-TiCl ₃ .h.atm)	t _m (min)	R _m	t _m						k ₂ (g-C ₃ H ₆ / g-TiCl ₃ .h ² .atm mmol-[A])	E ₂	k ₃ (h ⁻¹)	E ₃	k ₄ (h ⁻¹ .atm ⁻¹)	E ₄	k ₄ H ^{**}	k (l/mol)	Q	I.I. ^{***} (%)	M _v (x10 ⁻⁴)
AlEt ₃	160	9	190	5	32	35	10	1080	20	140	17	1.4	2~3	0.20	10	—	150	12	80	30
AlD ₃	75	90	85	8	33	37	11	210	—	40	17	0.4	~0	0.20	—	—	160	—	71	—
AlEt ₂ Cl	—	—	—	—	9.0	12.1	12	—	—	4.2	17	—	—	1.00	10.4 ± 1.2	18.9	110	1	91	50.6
AlEt ₂ Br	—	—	—	—	7.8	9.1	12	—	—	2.3	16	—	—	0.62	10.6 ± 1.3	2.92	100	0	97	46.6
AlEt ₂ I	5.7	90	8.5	16	0	10.4	13	—	—	3.0	17	0.2	15	0.52	9.8 ± 1.1	—	180	0	98	30.5

* Usual condition that p=66cmHg, TiCl₃=16 mmol/l, [AlR₃Y]=20 mmol/l.

** at 50°C.

*** I.I.% obtained by I.R. method for AlR₃ and by boiling n-heptane method for AlEt₂X.

present author holds here them only as the apparent characters of each alkylaluminum A. The experimental evidences by which the author proposes a new structure (III) have been obtained mainly from the following two kinds of experiment.

Elimination of Solute Organometallic Compound during Polymerization :

After polymerization was carried out for a given time (>4 min), the propene was substituted for nitrogen, the solution was removed and the residual solids were washed several times by pure n-heptane. This procedure is called as "Washing". After the washing, the same amount of n-heptane was admitted and the nitrogen was substituted for propene, then the polymerization was started again. The initial polymerization activity of the washed solids was the same with that of the catalyst system just before the washing, even after the washed solids were kept for various durations under nitrogen. However, the activity of the washed solids decreased gradually with increasing of polymerization time, as

$$-dR/dt = k_4 PR \quad (5)$$

In the presence of hydrogen of partial pressure P_H the decrease of the catalyst activity could be expressed by

$$-dR/dt = (k_4 P + k_4^H P_H) R \quad (6)$$

The isotacticity of polymers produced by the washed solids was the same with the original catalyst system while the viscosity of average molecular weight

was higher. Because the absence of solute alkylaluminum in the polymerization with the washed solids is responsible for the increase of molecular weight, the polymerization centers on the washed solids may be the same ones of the original catalyst system. The observed kinetics (5) shows that the gradual decrease of the catalyst activity of washed solids is due to monomer termination. Here, it should be noted that the value of k₄ is not the same but varies in accordance with the structure of alkylaluminum A, which suggests strongly that the polymerization centers formed with different alkylaluminum are not the same but different. If the polymerization centers had the same structure independent of organometallic compound used, as the monometallic theory requires, they must be deactivated by monomer or hydrogen with the same value of k₄ or k₄^H. The re-addition of the alkylaluminum to the washed solids deactivated by monomer resulted in the complete recovery of the catalyst activity. The recovery was almost the same with the initial increasing of polymerization rate in case B, which suggests us that the state of the washed solids after complete deactivation was the same one of the original TiCl₃ under monomer. It should be noted here that the washed solids obtained from the fresh catalyst mixtures, TiCl₃ and alkylaluminum, kept under nitrogen did not show any polymerization activity. Then, it is clear that only the mixing of TiCl₃ and alkylaluminum does not form at least the same polymerization centers with those of the catalysts during polymerization. From these experimental results we may have the following

scheme.

Center formation

Termination by monomer

Substitution of Solute Organometallic Compound during Polymerization :

The addition of another kind of organometallic compound B to the washed solids obtained from the catalyst system, $\text{TiCl}_3 + \text{A}$, used for polymerization, is called as "Substitution of A for B during polymerization". The experimental results obtained with many combinations of A and B are very interesting ones as shown in table 2. In all combinations examined the substitution of A for B caused the rapid change of kinetic curve (rate-time) from that of the polymerization with A to that with B, i. e., $R_A \rightarrow R_B$. For example, the substitution of

The mean life of polymerization centers on the washed solids are considerably long even in pure solvent, as described above, then the rapid decrease to R_B from R_A should be attributed to the rapid change in the polymerization centers as

The analysis of solution before and after the substitution $\text{AlEt}_3 \rightarrow \text{ZnEt}_2$ during the polymerization with TA-TiCl_3 , which was free from AlCl_3 , showed that total amount of Al in the solution was 0.1% of Ti after the washing and it increased to 0.8% after the substitution. The kinetics of the rapid decrease $R_A \rightarrow R_B$ could be expressed by

$$d(R_T - R_B)/d\tau = -k_5[B](R_T - R_B) \quad (13)$$

where τ was timed from the addition of B. The most striking results are the differences of k_5 values and of the activation energy E_5 in accordance with the combinations of A and B, as summarized in Table 2. Especially, the experimental results obtained from the combinations of the same B with different A give us important conclusion that different organometallic compounds form different polymerization centers. If the polymerization centers of the same structure were formed with different organometallic compounds, as the monometallic theory requires, they should be changed with the same rate constant

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTION OF ORGANOMETALLIC COMPOUND DURING POLYMERIZATION AT 41°C

A	B	Rate-time curve after substitution	Stereoregularity after substitution (%) (boiling n-heptane method)	k_5 (1/mmol h)	E_5 (kcal/mol)
AlEt_2Cl	AlEt_2Br	AlEt_2Br	97		
AlEt_2Cl	AlEt_2I	AlEt_2I	98		
AlEt_2Cl	AlEt_3	AlEt_3	64		
AlEt_2Cl	ZnEt_2	ZnEt_2	—		
AlEt_2Br	AlEt_3	AlEt_3	63		
AlEt_2Br	AlEt_2Cl	AlEt_2Cl	97 ± 1 (2 runs)		
AlEt_2I	AlEt_2Cl	AlEt_2Cl	98 ± 1 (3 runs)		
AlEt_2I	AlEt_3	AlEt_3	70		
AlEt_3	AlEtCl_2	AlEtCl_2	—	4.0	14.8 ± 1.6
AlEt_2Cl	AlEtCl_2	AlEtCl_2	—	2.6	16.5 ± 1.4
AlEt_2I	AlEtCl_2	AlEtCl_2	—	1.7	—
AlEt_3	CdEt_2	CdEt_2	—	5.1	—
AlEt_2Cl	CdEt_2	CdEt_2	—	1.1	—
AlEt_3	ZnEt_2	ZnEt_2	—	1.3	9.3 ± 0.4
AlEt_2	AlEt_2Cl	AlEt_2Cl	—	0.78	—
AlEt_3	AlEt_2I	AlEt_2I	—	0.71	—

AlEt_3 for AlEt_2Cl resulted in the rapid decrease in polymerization rate from R with AlEt_3 to R with AlEt_2Cl , vice versa. The substitution for AlEtCl_2 , which is almost inactive alkylaluminum, resulted in the rapid deactivation but the substitution from AlEtCl_2 for AlEt_2Cl resulted in the recovery to R with AlEt_2Cl . The effect of substitution, $A \rightarrow B$, in cases where $R_A < R_B$, may be explained by the formation of new centers C_B^* in addition to C_A^* . However, in case with $R_A > R_B$, this explanation can not be made.

k_5 on the substitution for the same organometallic compound B. Then, from the experimental results obtained, we have

The knowledge of the strength of metal-halogen bond may lead us to the supposition that the substitution of Ti-Br or Ti-I for Ti-Cl on the substitution

for AlEt_2Cl is not easy. So we can suppose that the stereospecificity of polymerization centers is governed mainly by the halogen (or alkyl) coordinated to Ti. By means of analysis of ^{13}C -NMR spectra Doi in author's laboratory demonstrated that the stereoregularity is not the end-group control but surface control⁹. The author and co-workers found that TiCl_3 pretreated by many bromine or iodine compounds, including poisonous ones, gives polymers of I. I 97~98% with the same rate as that with AlEt_2Cl , in the polymerization with AlEt_2Cl , which supports the above supposition.

Conclusion :

There are farther experimental results to be explained by this proposed mechanism. For example, the gradual decrease from R_m to R_∞ observed in the case with AlR_3 , which was before supposed by the present author as the result of two kinds of polymerization centers⁷, must be discussed in terms of the proposed mechanism. However, the author has stressed here the essential role of organometallic compound as the component of polymerization centers of working Ziegler-Natta catalysts, on the basis of new experimental results obtained from new kinetic technique, elimination and substitution of organometallic compound during polymerization.

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